

INNOVATION HUB

ELECTRIFICATION & ENERGY EFFICIENCY

NEFI Innovation Hubs are specialised networks led by renowned research institutions. They initiate highly relevant research and innovation projects.

Electrification & Energy Efficiency

Target groups: all sectors

Services offered by the NEFI Innovation Hubs

- NEFI Technology Talks:
A range of networking and information events
- Support throughout the entire innovation process: From project idea, application submission, to impact assessment
- Access to state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure
- Effective dissemination and exploitation of solutions and results

Electrification and energy efficiency are key levers for industrial transformation. On the one hand, the direct use of electricity from renewable sources plays an important role, while on the other hand, the electrification of process heat supply is gaining significance, as advances in efficient energy conversion and storage are increasingly making this possible. The successful integration of electrification into the entire process landscape and the efficient use of energy and resources are crucial.

KEY FOCUS AREAS

Electrification through the use of heat pumps for processes up to around 200°C

Electricity-based process heat generation for high-temperature applications (temperatures above 500°C)

Integration of thermal and electrical storage

Efficiency improvement through optimised energy distribution and process adaptation

CONTACT DETAILS

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HUB CO-LEADS

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